

SOYBEAN CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *In this article, you can get information about the chemical composition, protein, and carbohydrate content of soybeans, in what soil environment soybeans can grow well, the growing season of soybeans, and products made from soybeans.*

Keywords: *soy, protein, carbohydrate, fat, energy, calorie, grain, sorghum, marsh, flowering, branching, ripening, bean, Amigo, Sparta, Arlette, moisture, temperature.*

Today, soybean is a plant of special importance in the development of the food industry and the increase of livestock products, and it is rich in protein and high in calories among cultural plants due to its chemical composition, and in increasing soil fertility. When the chemical composition of soybean is organized, it contains 40-55% protein, 17-28% vegetable oil and essential amino acids and 12 different vitamins necessary for human health and body. Soybean belongs to the family of legumes and its origin is Central Asia. . Cereal contains 37-55% protein, 18-27% oil, various mixtures rich in carbohydrates, trace elements and vitamins. The favorable soil reaction for soybeans is pN-6.0-6.5. Since it is a heat-loving crop, it does not develop very well in marshy, marshy and heavy soils.

In terms of the size of cultivated areas in world agriculture, soybeans are second only to wheat, rice and corn. In the conducted researches, the length of the growing season was determined when the intermediate varieties of soybeans were planted in 3 different planting periods. Soybean cultivars took 6 days to germinate, 15-17 days to branch, 50-55 days to flower, 121-123 days to ripen, and 4-5 days to germinate, 14-15 days to branch, and 121-123 days to ripen. 50-52 days, ripening was 115-117 days. When the mid-ripe soybean variety was planted on May 10, the growing period was 121-123 days, which is considered an optimal period for the development of soybean crops. In order to study the effect of agrotechnics of soybean cultivation on the yield of seed material, research was conducted, according to the results of the research conducted for two years 93% yield was achieved when 500,000 viable seeds were sown in wide rows and 90% yield was achieved when 250,000 viable seeds were planted in wide rows. One of the unique features of soybean cultivation is that when most of its varieties enter the stage of fiber ripening, 75% of the leaves on the stem -85 percent is natural yellowing.

For the analysis of spring and summer soybeans, a sample is taken from a ripe fruit, and its average moisture content is found to be around 11-14%. When the soybean crop is fully ripe, it should be harvested in a short time, otherwise the loss of seed will increase sharply due to the opening of the pods and the spilling of seeds on the ground. possible It is appropriate to harvest when its seed moisture content reaches 16-18%. In soybeans, 2-12% of the total pods are located at the bottom of the stem, that is, up to 15 cm above the ground. Therefore, the combine harvester must be installed at a minimum height. Soil temperature is one of the most important indicators. If the soil is not warmed up well, the seed may rot or fungal diseases may appear, fertility will decrease, lawns will thin out, and weeds will invade. Soybean contains 30-52%

protein, 17-27% oil and 20% carbon water. The spread of soybeans on the earth is related to the quality of grain and protein. Oil, margarine, cheese, milk, flour, confectionary products, preserves are produced from soybeans. In the soil and climate conditions of our region, the norm of convenient irrigation of soybeans is 2500-3000 m³ per hectare. If we determine the rate of each watering from 500 m³, it means watering 5-6 times in this season. The seeds of soybean varieties were planted in the rates of 60, 70, and 80 kg, their morphology, biology and agrotechnics were organized, and the influence of these factors on the yield of soybeans was determined. It was found that after harvesting soybeans, the amount of humus in the soil increased by 2.54%, total nitrogen by 0.157%, phosphorus by 0.135%, and the amount of potassium by 2.25%. Soybean planting standards are determined depending on the size of the seed and the quick ripening of the variety. It was emphasized that getting good and high-quality crops from soybeans largely depends on planting seeds in a short period of time and using high-quality seeds. At the demonstration seminar on soybean agrotechnics, planting soybeans as the main crop in the conditions of our Republic should be done from April 15 to May 15, with the soil temperature not lower than 14 degrees. even in moisture, harvesting qigos, the growing period is 110-120 days when selecting varieties, the plant is 120-150 cm tall, the lower pods are located 14-20 cm above the soil surface, resistant to dormancy, the crop ripens at the same time and the grains do not flow, current It was noted that it is acceptable to plant Selekt-201 varieties, 75-80-day Amigo, Sparta, Arletta varieties for repeated crops. Soya root is a strongly developed white root that penetrates the soil to a depth of 2-2.5 m. Nitrogen-fixing nodules are observed 20-22 days after germination in the roots of plants planted after shade or planted in fields previously treated with Rhizobium. However, when soybeans are planted in the field without enrichment with Rhizobium in the first year, nitrogen fixers are almost not formed in the roots or very few nitrogen fixers are found. In researches, when analyzing the effect of nitrogen fertilization on the beginning of the legume phase of soybean varieties, in the control variant, Amigo variety in 2018, May 17, 2019 June 22, on June 07, 2020, on May 20, 2018, on June 20, 2019, on June 09, 2020 on the Tomaris-MAN-60 variety, on May 20, 2018, on June 22, 2019, on June 08, 2020 on the Oyjamol variety It was determined. When analyzing the effect of nitrogen fertilization on the period of the beginning of fiber ripening of soybean varieties, in the control variant, Amigo variety August 1, 2018, August 22, 2019, August 8, 2020, Tomaris-MAN-60 variety August 20, 2018, 2019 It was determined on September 10, 2020 on September 2, 2020, and on September 1, 2018, September 22, 2019, and September 3, 2020. , one time during the stage of sowing of soybeans, twice during the stage of flowering-podium, once during the stage of grain growth in the pods, one time more watering in the varieties with a long growing season, i.e. Tomaris-MAN-60 and Oyjamol varieties compared to other varieties in the experiment done.

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